

OCEAN ICE News – April 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to April's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community. Happy Easter!

We congratulate University of Delaware on becoming an associated partner in OCEAN ICE!

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including the upcoming webinars hosted by the European Polar Board, highlighting February's Climate Coffee and Argo float deployments by NASC and OCEAN ICE at The Danish Antarctic Science Seminar. We have upcoming Climate Coffees that you can register for in April, May and June. As well as participants that are planning to present at EGU. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in May!

Congratulations! University of Delaware is now an official associated partner in OCEAN ICE

Researcher in the Spotlight: Anastasiia Chyhareva

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Anastasiia Chyhareva, a meteorologist and climatologist working at [NASC](#) in Ukraine.

Read the feature on Anastasiia [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Webinar Series

The OCEAN ICE webinar series, hosted by the European Polar Board, is set to continue! The webinars offer insights into the OCEAN ICE project, showcasing ongoing research, key findings, and expected outcomes from various work packages.

On the 8th of April, EPB presented a webinar for WP7 on Data Management, here's a summary on what the webinar covered:

This is the third webinar in the series introducing the OCEAN ICE project. In this session, we explore data management within the project (Work Package 7 / WP7), with a special focus on using Jupyter Notebooks and Google Colab for polar research. Our invited speakers, Mariaclaudia Paolini (Project Manager, ETT) and Pietro Viglino (Backend Developer, ETT), present an overview of the OCEAN ICE Data Management Plan and infrastructure design, followed by a hands-on demonstration showing how these tools can be used to work with and elaborate research data. The webinar concludes with a public Q&A session. This series is hosted by the European Polar Board and moderated by Eva Horovcakova, EPB Senior Communications Officer. More about WP7: <https://ocean-ice.eu/about/project-st...>

Catch up on the webinar here: [OCEAN ICE WP7 Webinar - Data Management](#)

Don't miss out - join the conversation and stay informed about the latest developments of the project.

Read the description of the upcoming webinars **Upcoming events!**

OCEAN:ICE EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD

OCEAN ICE WP7 WEBINAR

DATA MANAGEMENT

This webinar will be the third in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

8 April 2025
14:00 CEST

@ Dr. Fenulka Ederhe

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe Funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – March's

Catch up on March's Climate Coffee with Sofia Darmaraki on Marine Heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea: A Literature Review [here](#).

Marine heatwaves (MHWs) are prolonged periods of exceptionally warm temperatures in the ocean, which have forced profound transformations in marine biodiversity and socio-economic systems globally over the last decades. The Mediterranean basin, a highly vulnerable area to climate change, has been particularly affected as a marginal sea, experiencing multifaceted changes due to these events. This presentation provides an overview of current understanding regarding the evolution of MHWs in the Mediterranean basin, from the past to the future, based on a recent literature review. Adopting an interdisciplinary perspective, we summarize the key driving mechanisms of MHWs, known feedbacks and impacts on various marine organisms and local economies while discussing ongoing challenges in their detection, characterization and monitoring.

20 March 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Sofia Darmaraki (FORTH)

**Marine Heatwaves in the Mediterranean
Sea: A Literature Review**

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

OCEAN ICE at ASSW

The [Arctic Science Summit Week](#) (ASSW) 2025, organised by IASC was held in Boulder, Colorado, from March 20-28. A key highlight was the [ICARP IV](#) Summit, uniting researchers, Indigenous representatives, and policymakers to shape Arctic research priorities for the next decade. The event also advanced preparations for the [Fifth International Polar Year \(2032–33\)](#). OCEAN ICE joined this important event as part of the [EU Polar Cluster](#) booth - participants attending ASSW had a chance to stop by throughout the whole conference to learn more about OCEAN ICE and other EU-funded projects, ask questions, and explore collaboration opportunities.

OCEAN ICE at The Danish Antarctic Science Seminar

OCEAN ICE was presented at the Danish Antarctic Science Seminar in early March. This annual meeting is an opportunity for the Danish Antarctic science community to get together and present new research, discuss new initiatives and to network and build collaborations across institutes.

Researchers shared recent findings, discussed collaborations, and showcased initiatives like the SCAR committee and a session on Antarctica InSync with an invited talk from Alexander Haumann. Highlights included data rescue efforts focused on aerial photos, data from the recent oldest ice core drilled at Little Dome C, remote sensing, as well as new dataset for Antarctic air temperatures based on MODIS surface temperatures and contributions to ESA's 4D Antarctica project, with strong contributions from early career researchers and a focus on fostering European collaborations.

OCEAN ICE Argo Float deployment - NASC

Ukrainian scientists have launched a new oceanographic research project: in March 2025, they installed 6 argobuoys in Antarctic waters. This is for the first time not only for our polar explorers studying the Southern Ocean but for Ukraine in general.

Argobuoys are innovative autonomous equipment for underwater measurements that have no engine and move with the current. They determine temperature, salinity, and pressure at different depths. Then, they transmit this data to a global database via satellite along with GPS coordinates. Currently, the data will be sent every 10 days. Thanks to these devices, scientists will be able to learn more about changes in currents in the Southern Ocean under the significant inflow of fresh water, as well as other processes. You can see what the "underwater assistants" look like and how they were launched in the video.

Watch the incredible video [here](#), which Features Natalia Shepel who is a part of WP1 in OCEAN ICE.

Article Written by [NASC](#)

OCEAN ICE - Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes Cross-Cutting Theme Meeting

The bi-annual cross-cutting theme meeting on Deep Uncertainty in Freshwater Fluxes (DUFF) was held on Tuesday 8 April. We heard 5 talks from across work packages, highlighting the strong synergies between different lines of research within OCEAN ICE. Freshwater fluxes are an important component of the Antarctic climate system, and DUFF focuses on how measurements of present-day fluxes (WP1-3) can be used to improve numerical ice-sheet simulations (WP4), and study the implications for regional ocean dynamics and the global climate system (WP5-6). Marte Hofsteenge (WP3) presented ongoing work on the comparison of surface runoff between different regional climate models; Yavor Kostov (WP1 and 6) presented work on the implementation of iceberg drifting, grounding and melt dynamics in NEMO; Nicolas Jourdain (WP2) presented results on the spatial distribution of iceberg melting as simulated by NEMO; Qing Qin (WP4) shared preliminary results on the calibration of ice-shelf basal melt parameterizations using an ensemble of ice-sheet model hindcast simulations; and David Chandler (WP5) presented an update on the implementation of future Antarctic freshwater flux estimates in NorESM. The next DUFF meeting is due to take place around the annual meeting in autumn.

OCEAN ICE WP3 Talks From NASC

NASC talks on particle tracking and melt from internal waves were recorded and are in the shared drive: [WP3-Ice sheet mass balance, forcing and dynamics](#)

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have five upcoming Climate Coffee events, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN:ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with David Chandler on Warming of circumpolar Deep Water
16 April 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

16 April 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Dave Chandler (NORCE)

Warming of circumpolar deep water: a million-year perspective on recent changes around Antarctica

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

Climate Coffee with Inga Sauer on Extreme weather events: tipping points & societal implications
22 May 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

22 May 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Inga Sauer (PIK)

Extreme weather events: tipping points and societal implications

The poverty implications of increasing frequencies of extreme weather events - identifying tipping points across households from different income groups

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino on Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project

12 June 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Pietro Viglino (ETT)

Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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the European Union

OCEAN ICE WP4 Webinar: Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing

Join us for the next webinar in the OCEAN ICE series, this time spotlighting Work Package 4 (WP4) dedicated to Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing.

This webinar will feature talks by: Jan De Rydt, Northumbria University (Introduction to Work Package 4) Frank Pattyn, Université Libre de Bruxelles (Deep Uncertainty in Freshwater Fluxes) Vio Coulon, Université Libre de Bruxelles (Future Freshwater Fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet) Qing Qin, Northumbria University (Calibration of Ice-Sheet Melt Parameterizations)

Date and time: 13th May, 10:30 CEST

Registration Here: [Webinar Registration - Zoom](#)

OCEAN ICE webinar series is facilitated by the [European Polar Board](#).

OCEAN:ICE **EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD**

OCEAN ICE WP4 WEBINAR

QUANTIFICATION OF ANTARCTIC ICE SHEET DEEP UNCERTAINTY AND FRESHWATER FLUXES UNDER CLIMATE FORCING

This webinar will be the fourth in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

13 May 2025
10:30 CEST

© Dr Renuka Badhe

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE EGU Participation

Some participants from OCEAN ICE plan to present at EGU:

Marte Hofsteenge:

I'm planning to present a poster in session CR2.2 – Ice-sheet and climate interactions.

The title is: Modelling future Antarctic climate and surface mass balance with RACMO2.4p1 (2015-2100).

Here a short summary:

We present results from future Antarctic climate simulations using the polar-adapted Regional Atmospheric Climate Model (RACMO2.4p1). Our study explores how the Antarctic surface mass balance (SMB) responds to two possible future climate scenarios, both based on the SSP3-7.0 pathway but simulated with different global climate models. We focus on changes in surface melt and investigate the temperature-melt relationship over Antarctic ice shelves, linking these with SEB components driving the strength of this relationship.

Andrew Meijers:

I'll be presenting OCEAN ICE related work on the future shutdown of Antarctic Bottom Water formation and subsequent climatic impacts under future climate change. This work uses CMIP6 climate models to show that under any future climate forcing scenario the formation of Antarctic bottom water, and the deep ocean overturning that this drives, collapses by around 50% over the coming century. The exact timing of this shutdown is set by internal variability in the models, but is initialised by present day warming, as even under strong climate mitigation emissions scenarios the shutdown still happens at the same rate. The work then goes on to show how this impacts Southern Ocean water mass properties and warming, and wider climate implications. It falls under WP5.

Max Brils:

Using data inversion to infer basal melt rates underneath ice shelves

The summary of the result's:

More than 80% of the grounded ice of the Antarctic ice sheet drains into the ocean through ice shelves. It is estimated that roughly half of the ice shelves' mass is eventually lost through melting from the underside, where the ice gets in contact with warmer ocean waters. Loss of these ice shelves could cause an increase of the discharge of grounded ice which would lead to additional sea-level rise. It is thus important to accurately quantify the rate at which ice shelves are melting if we wish to estimate future sea-level rise. Here, we present a novel methodology for estimating basal melt rates, by assimilating remotely derived estimates of surface velocities, ice sheet thickness, surface elevation changes and modelled surface mass balance using an ice sheet model (Ua). This methodology allows for a less noisy, physically consistent estimate of the ice mass divergence, and considers the uncertainty associated with each data product. The resulting estimates of the melt rate pattern at almost every Antarctic ice shelf is compared with previous remotely derived estimates.

Katie Lowery:

Presenting a poster on the relative importance of ice shelf geometry and ocean conditions on Pine Island Glacier melt rates over the last decade.

Birte Gülk:

The response of the Southern Ocean to freshwater hosing in an equilibrated 1° NEMO configuration with realistic ventilation

Xabier Davila:

Southern Ocean freshwater sources are quantified by identifying d18O-Salinity relationships through machine learning. Speaker: Xabier Davila. Title: Freshwater Sources and their Variability through Salinity-d18O Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem

Violaine Coulon

Future Freshwater Fluxes From the Antarctic Ice Sheet' and it is scheduled in room L3 on Tuesday, 29 April 2025, 08:35

Torsten Albrecht

A poster on this work will be presented:

Bathymetry-constrained impact of relative sea-level change on basal melting in Antarctica

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 15 April 2025, 11:00 CEST, OCEAN ICE Bottom Water and the Lower Cell Meeting - Cross Cutting theme meeting
- 27 April - 2 May 2025, [EGU General Assembly 2025](#), Vienna
- 8 May 2025, The Role of the Poles Cross-Cutting Theme Meeting
- 16 May, 11:00 CEST, Isotope Cross Cutting Theme Meeting, Online
- 2-13 June 2025, [United Nations Ocean Conference \(UNOC3\)](#), Nice
- 20-25 July 2025, [Busan IAMAS-IACS-IAPSO Joint Assembly 2025 \(JMCP20\)](#), the Republic of Korea

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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